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Case Study

A Descriptive Study to Assess the Knowledge and Practice about Respiratory Diseases in Tumkur Region

Adharsh Adhoni, Pavan G R, Roopa , Adarsh Meti, Akash Benakatti, Dr. R S Meghasri*

Akshaya Institute of Pharmacy, Tumkur, Karnataka, India.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The respiratory system is a vital biological system in the human body responsible for the process of breathing. This exchange of gas is essential for cellular respiration which provides the energy necessary for bodily functions. **Objective:** Descriptive study to assess the knowledge and practice about respiratory diseases through Tumkur region. **Methodology:** The prospective observational study was undertaken for a three-month period, data of our study was collected on basis of inclusion and exclusion criteria. **Result:** A total number of 250 participants was covered, males (134) and females (116). The participants particularly the age group belong to 20-30 years (44%) 30-40 (20%) 40-50 (17.2%) and 50-60 found to be (18.8%). The participants based on social habits like smoker (24%), alcoholic (20%), smoker and alcoholic (16%) and participants without habit are (40%). **Conclusion:** Through this study we concluded that the most of participants have better knowledge than the practice. The clinical pharmacist plays a crucial role in educating the participants regarding the diseases. The study highlights the need for conducting awareness program regarding, lifestyle modification and respiratory disease management among the participants.

INTRODUCTION

The respiratory system is one of the most vital systems in the human body, responsible for the exchange of oxygen and carbon dioxide that sustains life. This system includes the nose, nasal cavity, pharynx, larynx, trachea, bronchi, and lungs.

It ensures that oxygen enters the bloodstream to fuel cells and tissues, while also removing carbon dioxide, a waste product of metabolism. Because of its direct exposure to the external environment, the respiratory system is highly vulnerable to various infectious agents, allergens, pollutants, and chronic health conditions. Disorders affecting

***Corresponding Author:** Dr. R S Meghasri

Address: Akshaya Institute of Pharmacy, Tumkur, Karnataka, India.

Email ✉: pavanlavu2@gmail.com

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this system are commonly referred to as respiratory diseases.

Respiratory diseases represent a significant global health concern. They affect people of all age groups and socioeconomic backgrounds, and their burden is particularly severe in low- and middle-income countries where healthcare resources may be limited. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), hundreds of millions of

people suffer from chronic respiratory conditions, while acute infections like pneumonia remain among the leading causes of death in children under five years old. The prevalence of these diseases is also increasing due to rising pollution levels, smoking habits, occupational hazards, and lifestyle changes.

RESPIRATORY TRACT DISEASES

Respiratory Tract Diseases are Generally Divided into 2 Types

1. UPPER RESPIRATORY TRACT DISEASE (URTD):

Effects of the upper part of the respiratory system

- Common cold
- Sinusitis

- Pharyngitis
- Laryngitis
- Tonsillitis
- Corona virus

PATHOLOGY OF UPPER RESPIRATORY TRACT INFECTION

- Owing the great number of different viruses cause URIs
- It is probable that the histopathological changes during virous viral infection

- Influenza virus is thought to have an extensive direct cytopathic effect on respiratory epithelium.
- Which leads to degeneration of epithelial cells and parading the relative role of viruses in this condition will expand.

EXAMPLE:

SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS

DIAGNOSIS

- **Symptoms Assessment:** Doctors will inquire about your symptoms, their duration, and any recent exposure to sick individuals. Common symptoms include runny nose, sore throat, cough, fever and general malaise.
- **Medical History:** The health care provider will ask about your medical history, including any chronic condition or recent illnesses, to understanding your health status.
- **Physical Examination:** This involves checking signs of disease in your ear, nose and throat. They may use stethoscope to listen to your breathing and check for any abnormal sounds in your lungs.

- **Further Testing:** In case where symptoms are severe or complication are suspected and additional test like:
- **Sputum Test:** If there is a persistent cough, a sample of mucus may be collected to check for bacteria.
- **CT scan:** To get more detail images of the lungs, especially if there's a suspicion of a more serious condition.
- **Bronchoscopy:** In rare case, a thin, flexible tube with a camera may be inserted into the airway to visualize and potentially collect sample for testing.

DRUG TREATMENT

DRUG	DOSING	DURATION OF TREATMENT
ACETAMINOPHEN	500 TO 1000 mg	SINGLE DOSE
INTRANASAL OXYMETAZOLINE	2 SPRAY (0.05%) PER NOSTRIL 1 OR 2 TIMES PER DAY	UPTO 10 DAYS
AZITHROMYCIN	500mg PER DAY	3 TO 10 DAYS
IBUPROFEN	400mg 4 TO 6 HOURS	MORE THAN 10 DAYS
DEXTROMETHAORPHAN	2 TSP (10ml) EVERY 4 HOURS	EVERY 4 TO 12 HOURS
AOMOXICILLIN	500mg EVERY 8 HOURS	UPTO 10 DAYS
PENCILLIN	500mg EVERY 6 TO 8 HOURS	UPTO 10 DAYS
PAXLOVID (combination of nirmatrelvir and ritonavir)	1 NIRMATRELVIR 150mg AND 1 RITONAVIR 100mg (taken in combination)	UPTO 5 DAYS
LEVOFLOXACIN	500mg ONCE A DAY	10 TO 14 DAYS

2. LOWER RESPIRATORY TRACT DISEASE

- Tuberculosis
- Asthma
- Lung abscess

Affects the lower airways, including the:

- Bronchitis
- Pneumonia

PATHOLOGY OF LOWER RESPIRATORY TRACT DISEASE

SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS

Diagnosis:

- **Symptoms Assessment:** A doctor will usually diagnose a lower respiratory infection. during an exam and after discussing the symptoms a person has and how long they have been present.
- During the exam, the doctor will listen to the person’s chest and breathing through stethoscope.

- The doctor may order tests to help diagnose the problem, such as:
 - Pulse oximetry to find how much oxygen is in the blood.
 - chest X-rays to check for pneumonia.
 - blood tests to check for bacteria and viruses.
 - mucus samples to look for bacteria and viruses.

DRUG TREATMENT

DRUG	DOSING	DURATION TIME
ISONIAZID	300mg ONCE A DAY	UPTO 6 MONTHS
TURBUTALINE	5mg 3 TIMES A DAY	AS PRESCRIBED BY PHYSICIAN
LEVALBUTEROL	1.25mg PER DAY	AS PRESCRIBED BY PHYSICIAN
N-ACETYLCYSTEINE	600mg PER DAY	72 HOURS
ETHAMBUTOL	50mg ONCE IN A DAY	1 TO 2 YEARS OR MORE
AOMOXICILLIN	500mg EVERY 8 HOURS	UPTO 10 DAYS
PENICILLIN V	500mg EVERY 12 HOURS	UPTO 10 DAYS

AIM:

A Descriptive study to assess the knowledge and practice about respiratory disease in Tumkur region

- The study will be conducted for 3 months.

Study design:

- Descriptive observation study.

OBJECTIVES:

- To assess the knowledge and practice among different respiratory diseases
- To educate the community about respiratory diseases and its complications
- To educate the community about the primary prevention of respiratory disease
- To compare the knowledge and practices regarding respiratory tract disease

Purposed sample size:

- More than 230.

Source of data:

- Direct interaction with patient
- Patient case study sheets

Study criteria:

- The study was carried out by considering the following inclusion and exclusion criteria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study site:

- The study will be carried out in the community of Tumkur region.

Inclusion criteria:

- Patient age more than 18 years.
- Both the gender.

Duration of study:

- Patient diagnosed with (or) without respiratory disease.
- Those who willing to participate the study.
- Submission of report.

Exclusion criteria:

- Age below 18 years.
- Special population (pregnancy and lactating woman).
- Patient who are having communicable diseases like (HIV & AIDS).
- Those who are not willing to participate in the study.

Study procedure:

- Regarding this project piolet study has been done.
- Collection and review of literature prepare to the project.
- Prepare the study protocol including the study design and design of perform.
- Enrolment of patients according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- Taken patient consent.
- Collection of patient details from the direct interaction with patient and patient case sheet.
- Assess the knowledge and practice with the help of questionnaires.
- Provide the counselling to the patient.
- Provide patient information leaflets.
- The obtain information was analysed and represented in the form of table and graphs and data was analysed statically.

Materials used:

- Informed consent form
- Patient profile form
- K and P questionnaires

Methods:

- Data were collected from patient profile documents.
- The medical history consisting of in-patient, medical, records was reviewed.
- Data was recorded as patient demographic information, clinical status, duration of disease and type of complication

Results:

A descriptive study was collected for 3 months among respiratory diseases participants residing in Tumkur region on the community basis. a total number of 250 participants during the study period. out of 250 participants, 134 (53.6) were males and 116 (49.4) were females.

Table 01: Distribution of patients according to gender

Gender	Total no. of participants (N=250)	Percentage
Males	134	53.6%
Females	116	48.4%

Among 250 participants, age range from 18 years to participants above 50 years. They are categorised into 4 groups, among these groups majority of the participants were from age above 20 i.e., 110 participants (44%) and only 13 participants (5.2%) were from age between 40- 50 years.

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to age groups

Age (years)	No of participants (N=250)	Percentage
20-30	110	44%
30-40	50	20%
40-50	43	17.2%
50-60	47	18.8%

Distribution of 250 participants based on social habits was in 3 categories namely Smokers, Alcoholic, and smoker and Alcoholic. Among 250 participants were neither smokers nor alcoholic and were found to be smokers and alcoholic

Table 03: Distribution of participants based on social habits

Categories	No. of participants (N= 250)	Percentage
Smoker	60	24%
Alcoholic	50	20%
Smoker & alcoholic	40	16%
Nil	100	40%

Table 04: Assessment of knowledge

Sr. No	Questions	% of Correct Response (yes)	% of Wrong Response (No)
1	Are you practicing any prevention measure / parameters for respiratory tract disease?	83.2%	16.8%
2	Are you experiencing a persistent cough?	78.4%	21.6%
3	Have you frequently do you practice these measures?	77.2%	22.8%
4	Are you practice hand washing?	54%	46%
5	Do you practice hand hygiene after every episode of coughing or sneezing?	81.2%	18.8%
6	Are you producing more mucus or phlegm than usual?	88%	12%
7	If you practicing any parameters of respiratory tract disease?	64.8%	35.2%
8	Have you had frequent respiratory infection recently?	31.6%	68.4%

Table 05: Assessment of practice

Sr. no	Questions	% of Correct Response (yes)	% of Wrong Response (No)
1	Have you ever about respiratory tract disease?	50.4%	49.6%
2	Have you known about transmission of respiratory tract diseases?	35.6%	64.4%
3	There are any ways to prevent transmission of respiratory tract disease?	52.4%	47.6%
4	You have any source of information?	90.4%	9.6%
5	Do you know about respiratory hygiene?	83.6%	16.4%
6	Do you know about hand hygiene?	39.2%	60.8%
7	Can cough and sneezing prevent spread of disease to others?	36%	64%
8	Do you have chest pain when you breath or cough?	31.6%	68.4%

Comparison of YES response between assessment of knowledge & practice Questionaries

Yes, response is compared between both assessment of knowledge and assessment of

practice Questionaries. In these 69.05% participants showed response for assessment of knowledge questionaries and only 52.4% participants showed response for assessment of practice questionaries.

DISCUSION

Respiratory disease are the conditions affecting the lungs and airways, which can range from mild infections like common cold to chronic and life-threatening conditions such has chronic abstractive pulmonary disease (COPD). abstractive diseases: this causes narrowed or blocked airways, making it difficult to exhale, include asthma and COPD. Restrictive disease:

this involves a reduced lung capacity, as seen in condition like pulmonary fibrosis. infectious diseases caused by virus or bacteria, include pneumonia, tuberculosis and covid19.

In a descriptive study conducted over 3 months among respiratory disease participants in Tumkur region community basis, several key findings were observed from 250 participants. Here the gender distribution of 250 participants, 134 (53.6%) were

males, and 116 (48.4%) were females. The age of the participants ranged from 20 years to above 50 years.

Participants were categorized into 4 age group that are 110 (44%) participants belong to the age group of 20-30 years, 50 (20%) participants belong to age group of 30-40 years, 43 (17.2%) participants belong to age group of 40-50 years, 47 (18.8%) participants belong to age group of 50 to above 50. the majority of participants the participants fell in to the age group of 20-30 years, accounting to the above data.

When we investigate the social habit of participant were divided into 4 categories based on social habits as follows smokers, alcoholic, smokers and alcoholic and nil the majority of participants (40%) neither smokers nor alcoholic. 24% were smokers, 20% were alcoholics, and 16% were both smokers and alcoholics.

CONCLUSION

This study was carried out to assess the knowledge, practice and awareness regarding respiratory tract disease in Tumkur region.

This study reveals that male participants are more participated than females. In this survey identified that majority of participants from 20-30 age group.

Based on the assessment of knowledge levels that majority of participants had good knowledge about respiratory tract disease.

Based on the assessment of practice levels that majority of participants had poor practice regarding respiratory diseases.

The practice of maintaining of self-hygiene to avoid the respiratory disease was low.

It's important to aware about the signs and symptoms, risk factors, causes of respiratory disease that help in practicing healthy habits.

So, to reduce the respiratory diseases it requires standardized publicity and education strategies and good treatment facilities in order to improve the public health.

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